

SPECTRALLY ENCODED, MULTICARRIER PSK COMMUNICATION IN A MULTIPATH CHANNEL

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Abstract

This research examines the performance of a spectrally encoded, multicarrier, phase shift keying communications system in a frequency-selective, slowly-fading (FSSF) Rayleigh multipath channel. The literature discusses several frequency domain techniques including spectral encoding that have been used for interference avoidance and multiple access techniques. This research applies spectral encoding to mitigate the effects of multipath fading.

Analysis and Matlab® simulations compare the performance of spectrally encoded and unencoded signals through a multipath fading channel using an L-diversity RAKE receiver. Encoded signals take on the spectral shape of the fading channel transfer function magnitude spectrum. Unencoded signals have a flat magnitude spectrum.

Research results indicate for diversities (L) ranging between 2 and 50, spectrally encoded signals need 1.0 to 2.75dB less transmitted normalized bit energy to noise power spectral density ratios (E_b/N_o) to achieve the same probability of bit error (P_b) as unencoded signals.

Introduction

The literature mentions several frequency domain techniques used in communications. In the 1980s and 1990s several authors applied transform domain filtering techniques for interference avoidance [1, 2, 3]. Falconer demonstrated equalization is more computationally efficient in the frequency domain for broadband systems where intersymbol interference spans 100s of symbols [4]. Spectral encoding describes techniques that apply a "spreading sequence" in the frequency domain to encode multiple access information or avoid interference [5]. Multicarrier CDMA (MC-CDMA) and spread time CDMA are also

techniques that use pseudo random codes in the frequency domain [6, 7].

This research uses spectral encoding at the transmitter to combat the adverse effects of multipath fading. There are other techniques such as time reversal [8] and adaptive coded modulation [9], which alter transmitted waveforms to overcome multipath effects. However, to the authors' knowledge this is the first application of spectral encoding to mitigate multipath fading.

Spectral Encoding in a Multicarrier System

This research analyzes and simulates a communications system very similar to MC-CDMA described by Hara [6]. The difference lies in the implementation of the spectral encoding algorithm. This system encodes information in both the amplitude and phase of the spectral components.

Diagrams of a transmitter and a receiver are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The components that generate the fundamental signaling waveforms (FSWs) are the heart of the system. The system constructs FSWs from a series of orthogonal complex exponentials corresponding to spectral components. The amplitudes and phases of each spectral component can be independently assigned to create FSWs with desirable spectral characteristics. In this research, the goal is to mitigate multipath fading.

The operation of the transmitter starts with a spectral estimation to determine the current spectral environment. Assume the environment is digitally sampled at twice the highest frequency of interest. The spectral encoding algorithm assigns the amplitudes of the FSW spectral components. The scaling operation ensures equal energy signaling. The phase generator assigns independent phases to each frequency component to either provide multi-access separation or make the FSW more featureless in the time domain [10].

Figure 1. PSK Transmitter Block Diagram

Figure 2. PSK Receiver Block Diagram

For M -ary Phase Shift Keying (PSK) each of $M=2^1$ data phases, θ_k , are uniformly added to the phases of all spectral components prior to the inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT). The output of the IDFT is a set of M FSWs corresponding to the set of M data phases. To modulate data, the transmitter converts 1 data bits to one of M symbols. The FSW for each symbol is then converted from digital to analog to modulate each symbol. The FSWs may also be carrier modulated before amplification and transmission through the channel.

The receiver generates FSWs using the same technique discussed for the transmitter. We assume the transmitter and receiver are perfectly synchronized and construct identical FSWs. The

receiver uses the complex conjugates of the FSWs as reference waveforms for the matched filter demodulators performing coherent phase detection. Previous research demonstrated that well-known M -ary PSK bit error rate expressions accurately predict the bit error rates for coherent M -ary PSK in this type of system [10]. This research uses binary PSK (BPSK) exclusively. Probability of bit error for BPSK systems is given by [11]:

$$P_b = Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2E_b}{N_o}}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where $Q(x)$ is:

$$Q(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_x^{\infty} e^{-x^2/2} dx, \quad x \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

Additionally, E_b/N_o is the bit energy to noise power spectral density (PSD) ratio, or signal to noise ratio (SNR).

Multipath Fading

Multipath fading is a reality of wireless communications environments that degrades bit error performance. Based on the characteristics of the channel and the communications system, the multipath channel can be modeled in different ways. This research models the channel as a Rayleigh faded, frequency-selective, slowly-fading multipath channel. Rayleigh fading is typical of environments where there is no predominant line-of-sight component (e.g. urban environments) [11]. To be considered frequency-selective, the system bandwidth must greatly exceed the channel coherence bandwidth [11]. The symbol rate must be much longer than the channel coherence time for the channel to be considered slowly-fading. Previous research indicates that these assumptions are reasonable given typical cell phone channel characteristics and communications system parameters [12].

Figure 3. Tapped Delay Line Model of a Multipath Fading Channel

Figure 3 shows a frequency-selective, slowly-fading multipath channel modeled as a tapped delay line. The coefficients of each delay tap, c_n , are complex Gaussian random variables for a Rayleigh faded channel [11]. The additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) process, $z(t)$, is stationary with noise PSD of N_o . If the communications system baseband bandwidth is W_{BB} , and the system at baseband is sampled at $2W_{BB}$, the delay taps are $1/(2W_{BB})=T_{samp}$ long [11]. Equations (3) and (4) give the complex, low-pass representations of the channel impulse response and transfer function [12]. In (3), L is the number of delay taps in the model and corresponds to the number of delay paths modeled. The transfer function in (4) is the Fourier transform of the impulse response.

$$h_l(t) = \sum_{n=1}^L c_n \delta(t - nT_{samp}) \quad (3)$$

$$H_l(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h_l(\tau) e^{-j2\pi f\tau} d\tau \quad (4)$$

The corresponding discrete-time and frequency complex, low-pass representations of the channel impulse response and transfer function are given by (5) and (6). The transfer function is computed using an N-point DFT.

$$h_l[n] = \sum_{i=1}^L c_i \delta[i - n] = \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i e^{j\theta_i} \delta[i - n] \quad (5)$$

$$H_l[m] = \sum_{n=1}^L c_n e^{j2\pi mn/N} \quad m \in [0, N-1] \quad (6)$$

$$H_l[m] = C_m \equiv H_m e^{i\theta_m} \quad (7)$$

The RAKE receiver is one method of overcoming the detrimental effects of the multipath channel by employing diversity in the communications system. A full explanation of the RAKE receiver is presented in [11]. Simply stated, the RAKE receiver leverages the reflected replicas of the transmitted signal as a source of diversity. Assuming the communications system can accurately estimate the channel impulse response, the RAKE receiver convolves the channel impulse response with the FSWs and uses the result in the matched filters of the demodulator. Assuming the FSWs have an impulse-like autocorrelation function, so that delayed replicas of the FSWs cause no self interference, the resulting probability of bit error relationship for a RAKE receiver, $P_{b,RAKE}$, is:

$$P_{b,RAKE} = \mathbf{E} \left[Q \left(\sqrt{2\gamma_b} \right) \right]_{\gamma_b} \quad (8)$$

In (8), $\mathbf{E}[\bullet]_{\gamma_b}$ denotes the expected value over the random variable γ_b and γ_b is the bit energy to noise PSD ratio *received* through the multipath channel. The received SNR is related to the transmitted E_b/N_o by (9).

$$\gamma_b = \frac{E_b}{N_o} \sum_{n=1}^L \alpha_n^2 \quad (9)$$

As mentioned above, the advantage of using spectral encoding in a communications system is the capability to design waveforms with desirable spectral characteristics. In this research, the premise is that spectral encoding can mitigate the negative effects of multipath fading. To illustrate, Figure 4 and Figure 5 display a typical channel impulse response and associated transfer function from a single instantiation of a Rayleigh FSSF multipath channel with $L=16$ delay taps. A 128-point DFT computes the transfer function. Figure 5 demonstrates the key point: it is desirable to shape the spectrum of the FSWs so little or no energy is placed in frequencies the channel will attenuate. To mitigate multipath fading, the spectral encoding algorithm in this research shapes the FSW spectral amplitudes using the magnitude of the channel transfer function. The resulting shape of the encoded FSWs deemphasizes spectral components the channel attenuates and emphasizes spectral components the channel passes.

Figure 4. Multipath Channel Impulse Response

Figure 5. Multipath Channel Transfer Function

The remainder of this paper discusses the analysis of a RAKE receiver comparing spectrally encoded and unencoded signals through a FSSF multipath channel.

Analysis

Fundamental Signaling Waveforms

The analysis begins with the time representation of a typical FSW. In (10), l indicates the complex low-pass representation and k references the k^{th} of M data symbols; $P-1$ is the number of sinusoids used to construct the FSW. A_p is the amplitude of each spectral component. f_{sb} is the fundamental frequency of the FSW, all other frequencies are integer multiples of f_{sb} . ϕ_p is the

encoded phase of each individual spectral component, and θ_k is the data phase for the FSW. Since (10) is the complex low-pass representation, the FSW is a sum of complex exponentials [12].

$$s_{l,k}(t) = \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} A_p \exp[j(2\pi f_{sb} p t + \phi_p + \theta_k)] \quad (10)$$

The energy in a symbol duration for the continuous time representation is derived in (11). The symbol duration is the period of the fundamental frequency, $T_{sb}=1/f_{sb}$. Note that since the individual frequency components are orthogonal, the symbol energy simplifies quite nicely.

$$E_{sym} = E_b = \int_0^{T_{sb}} s_{l,k}(t) s_{l,k}^*(t) dt = T_{sb} \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} A_p^2 \quad (11)$$

Assuming the system at baseband is sampled at $f_{samp}=2P f_{sb}=N f_{sb}$ to avoid aliasing, the discrete-time, complex low-pass representation of the FSW is in (12) [12].

$$s_{l,k}[n] = \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} A_p \exp\left[j\left(2\pi p \frac{n}{N} + \phi_p + \theta_k\right)\right] \quad (12)$$

An N -point DFT of $s_{l,k}[n]$ gives the discrete-frequency representation of the FSW shown in (13).

$$S_{l,k}[m] = \begin{cases} A_m e^{j(\phi_m + \theta_k)} & \forall m \in [0, P-1] \\ A_{m-N} e^{j(\phi_{m-N} + \theta_k)} & \forall m \in [P, N-1] \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Using Parseval's relation and the discrete frequency representation in (13), equation (14) derives the energy for single symbol duration.

$$E_{sym} = E_b = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} |S[k]|^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} A_p^2 \quad (14)$$

RAKE Receiver for Spectrally Encoded Signals

Now the RAKE receiver design is applied to the multicarrier system. As shown in Figure 6, the receiver constructs the FSWs as described before. The complex conjugates of the FSWs are delayed

and scaled using the complex conjugate of the estimated channel impulse response. The sums of delayed and scaled FSWs are the reference waveforms for the matched filters.

Figure 6. RAKE Receiver

The received signal, $r_{l,k}(t)$, after traversing the channel model shown in Figure 3, is described by the equations below, where $z_l(t)$ is a stationary AWGN process.

$$r_{l,k}(t) = \sum_{n=1}^L c_n s_{l,k}(t - nT_{\text{samp}}) + z_l(t) \quad (15)$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^L \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} c_n A_p e^{j[2\pi f_{sb} p(t - nT_{\text{samp}}) + \phi_p + \theta_k]} + z_l(t) \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) above clearly demarcates the signal and noise components of $r_{l,k}(t)$. If the signal component is denoted $v_{l,k}(t)$, as shown in (17), the RAKE receiver effectively uses $v_{l,k}^*(t)$ as the reference waveforms in the matched filters.

$$v_{l,k}(t) = \sum_{n=1}^L \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} c_n A_p e^{j[2\pi f_{sb} p(t - nT_{\text{samp}}) + \phi_p + \theta_k]} \quad (17)$$

Using the above expressions for $r_{l,k}(t)$ and $v_{l,k}(t)$, (19) shows the expression for the i^{th} test statistic in the RAKE receiver, Z_i .

$$Z_i = \text{Re} \left\{ \int_0^{T_{sb}} r_{l,k}(t) v_{l,i}^*(t) dt \right\}; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (18)$$

$$Z_i = \text{Re} \left\{ \int_0^{T_{sb}} v_{l,k}(t) v_{l,i}^*(t) dt + \dots \int_0^{T_{sb}} z_l(t) v_{l,i}^*(t) dt \right\}; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (19)$$

$$Z_i = \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbf{V} + \int_0^{T_{sb}} z_l(t) v_{l,i}^*(t) dt \right\}; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (20)$$

From the expression in (20), it is clear that the first term, \mathbf{V} , corresponds to the energy in the received signal, while the second is the contribution from the noise. Since the performance of a matched filter demodulator is directly related to the SNR in the test statistic, this equation is the basis for the performance analysis of the RAKE receiver. The

spectrally encoded and unencoded signals are analyzed separately.

Unencoded Analysis

These signals apply no spectral encoding, therefore all of the frequency components (except DC and Nyquist) have equal amplitudes. Starting with (11), (21) gives the relationship between A_p and E_b .

$$A_p = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{E_b}{T_{sb}(N-2)}} & \forall p \in (-P, P-1], p \neq 0 \\ 0 & \forall p = -P, 0 \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Using the relationships in (17) and (21), the expressions below simplify the signal energy contribution to the test statistic for unencoded signals (V_{Un}). Equation (22) substitutes the alternate magnitude and phase representation of the impulse response coefficients ($\alpha_n e^{i\Theta_n} = c_n$).

$$V_{Un} = \text{Re} \left[\int_0^{T_{sb}} \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^L \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} \alpha_n e^{j\Theta_n} A_p e^{j[2\pi f_{sb} p(t-nT_{samp}) + \phi_p + \theta_k]} \right\} \times \left[\sum_{m=1}^L \sum_{q=-P}^{P-1} \alpha_m e^{-j\Theta_m} A_q e^{-j[2\pi f_{sb} q(t-mT_{samp}) + \phi_q + \theta_l]} \right] dt \right] \quad (22)$$

For the analysis of the test statistic of interest (i.e., $i=k$), the expression above simplifies to a quadruple sum over n, m, p and q which is analyzed in four different cases.

Case 1: When $p=q$ and $n=m$, all of the exponential terms in the quadruple sum cancel and the expression quickly simplifies to (23).

$$V_1 = \text{Re} \left\{ \int_0^{T_{sb}} \sum_{n=1}^L \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} \alpha_n^2 A_p^2 dt \right\} \quad (23)$$

None of the terms in (23) are time dependent, so the integral simplifies to T_{sb} . Since all of the A_p are equal, the summation over p yields $(N-2)$ terms of A_p^2 , and (23) simplifies as shown in (24).

$$V_1 = T_{sb} (N-2) A_p^2 \sum_{n=1}^L \alpha_n^2 \quad (24)$$

$$V_1 = T_{sb} (N-2) \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_b}{T_{sb}(N-2)}} \right)^2 \sum_{n=1}^L \alpha_n^2 \quad (25)$$

$$V_1 = E_b \sum_{n=1}^L \alpha_n^2 \quad (26)$$

Recall that the α_n are the magnitudes of independent, identically distributed (i.i.d), complex Gaussian random variables, therefore the expression for V_1 is a sum of L i.i.d. Chi-squared random variables with 2 degrees of freedom. The sum V_1 is scaled to have a mean energy of E_b as shown in the probability density function (pdf) in (27) [12].

$$f_{V_1}(V_1) = \frac{1}{(L-1)! E_b^L} V_1^{L-1} e^{-V_1/E_b} \quad (27)$$

Case 2: The second case of the unencoded signal energy contribution to the test statistic occurs with $p=q$ and $m \neq n$. The quadruple sum simplifies first to a triple sum and the time dependence is removed from within the integral.

$$V_2 = \text{Re} \left\{ T_{sb} \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} A_p^2 \sum_{n=1}^L \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq n}}^L c_n c_m^* e^{j[2\pi f_{sb} T_{samp}(m-n)]} \right\} \quad (28)$$

By substituting $1/(2P f_{sb}) = T_{samp}$, and using the expression for A_p from (21), V_2 simplifies to (29).

$$V_2 = \text{Re} \left\{ T_{sb} \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_b}{T_{sb}(N-2)}} \right)^2 \times \dots \left[\sum_{\substack{p=-P+1 \\ p \neq 0}}^{P-1} \sum_{n=1}^L \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq n}}^L c_n c_m^* e^{\frac{j p \pi}{P}(m-n)} \right] \right\} \quad (29)$$

Noting that within (29), the random variables c_n and c_m^* are i.i.d., it is assumed that the product $c_n c_m^*$ can be treated as a constant within the summation. The product is renamed $c_n c_m^* = C$ and removed from the summation as shown in (30).

$$V_2 = \text{Re} \left[\frac{E_b}{(N-2)} C \sum_{\substack{p=-P+1 \\ p \neq 0}}^{P-1} \sum_{n=1}^L \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq n}}^L e^{\frac{j p \pi}{P}(m-n)} \right] \quad (30)$$

The simplification of the triple sum in (30) is derived in [12] with the result shown in (31).

$$V_2 \approx \text{Re} \left\{ \frac{E_b}{(N-2)} \mathbf{C} [-L(L-2)] \right\} \quad (31)$$

$$V_2 \approx E_b \left[\frac{-L(L-2)}{N-2} \right] \text{Re} \{ \mathbf{C} \} \quad (32)$$

To simplify the analysis, it is assumed that the real part of the product $\text{Re} \{ \mathbf{C} \}$ is approximately equal to the product of the magnitudes of the two independent, complex Gaussian random variables $(\alpha_n \alpha_m)$. Then it can be shown that the density of V_2 is the pdf of the scaled product of two Rayleigh random variables given by (33) [12].

$$f_{V_2}(V_2) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{|A| |w| \sigma^4} \exp \left\{ w^2 + \left(\frac{V_2}{Aw} \right)^2 \right\} dw \quad (33)$$

where:

$$A = -E_b \left[\frac{L(L-2)}{N-2} \right] \quad (34)$$

Cases 3 and 4: When $p \neq q$, $m=n$ and $p \neq q$, $m \neq n$, the derivation in [12] demonstrates that the sums for V_3 and V_4 equal zero when integrated over $(0, T_{sb})$ since the summations occur over products of orthogonal complex exponentials.

The final step for the unencoded test statistic analysis is determining the pdf for the received SNR, γ_{un} . Since the signal energy contribution is the sum of V_1 and V_2 , and the noise PSD is N_o , γ_{un} is expressed in (35) and (36).

$$\gamma_{un} = \frac{V_1 + V_2}{N_o} \quad (35)$$

$$\gamma_{un} = \frac{E_b}{N_o} \left[\sum_{n=1}^L \alpha_n^2 - \left(\frac{L(L-2)}{N-2} \right) \text{Re} \{ \mathbf{C} \} \right] \quad (36)$$

The pdf for γ_{un} is determined by convolving the pdfs of V_1 and V_2 , then scaling by the constant $1/N_o$ [13]. We achieved no closed form solution for the distribution of γ_{un} . Therefore numerical solutions for the pdf of γ_{un} , and $E \left[Q \left(\sqrt{2\gamma_{un}} \right) \right]_{\gamma_{un}}$ solve the analytical P_b prediction. Figure 7 illustrates the analytical results for unencoded RAKE P_b performance.

Figure 7. Analytical Results: Unencoded

Encoded Analysis

The next step in the analysis covers the RAKE demodulator test statistic for spectrally encoded signals. Since the spectral magnitudes A_p of the FSWs for the encoded signals are not all equal, the analysis takes place in the frequency domain.

The spectral encoding algorithm uses the magnitudes of the channel transfer function as the basis for the amplitudes of the transmitted signal spectra. They are scaled by a constant, K , to ensure equal-energy signaling. Using the definition of the transfer function magnitudes in (7), the discrete-frequency representation of the transmitted, spectrally encoded signals is:

$$S_{i,k}[m] = KH_m e^{j(\phi_m + \theta_k)}; \quad m \in [0, N-1] \quad (37)$$

Where [12]:

$$K = \sqrt{\frac{E_b N}{\sum_{m=0}^{N-1} H_m^2}} \quad (38)$$

After passing through the channel, the discrete frequency representation of the received signal is:

$$R_{i,k}[m] = KH_m^2 e^{j(\phi_m + \theta_k + \theta_m)}; \quad m \in [0, N-1] \quad (39)$$

Recall that V denotes the signal energy contribution in the test statistic. Using (14), the encoded signal energy contribution, V_{Enc} is computed from the amplitudes of $R_{i,k}[m]$. Since

$m \in [0, N-1]$, the summation over the spectral amplitudes is changed from $[-P, P-1]$ to $[0, N-1]$.

$$V_{Enc} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{p=-P}^{P-1} A_p^2 \quad (40)$$

$$V_{Enc} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} (KH_m^2)^2 \quad (41)$$

$$V_{Enc} = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_b N}{\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} H_k^2}} \right)^2 \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} H_m^4 \quad (42)$$

$$V_{Enc} = E_b \frac{\sum_{m=0}^{N-1} H_m^4}{\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} H_k^2} \quad (43)$$

Again, the distribution of V_{Enc} must be determined then scaled by $1/N_o$ to determine the distribution of the received SNR for the spectrally encoded signals, γ_{Enc} . The joint densities of H_p^4 and H_p^2 are unknown; therefore, neither analytic nor numerical solutions are known. Instead, Monte Carlo simulations and distribution parameter estimation methods estimate the distribution of the ratio in (43).

Monte Carlo simulations of the random sequence c_n are the basis for the computations. From each L -length sequence of c_n , the resultant frequency domain terms H_m^2 and H_m^4 are computed using a zero-padded, N -point DFT ($N = 2P$). The summations of H_m^2 and H_m^4 are then computed and divided as in (43). The simulation terminates when the 95% confidence interval on the sample mean of the division converges to within 0.1% of the computed value. After the simulation converges, Matlab® parameter estimation routines process the data for several distributions. Based on visual inspection of the histograms, the program tests the Monte Carlo data against the Gamma, Rayleigh, Log-Normal and Weibull distributions. Once the parameters for each of these four distributions are known, the routine determines the distribution that most closely matches the simulation data using quantile-quantile plots and linear regression models [12]. Table 1 lists the results of the parameter estimations for $L = 2, 4, 20$ and 50 given $P=1024$.

Table 1. Received SNR Distributions, γ_{Enc} [12]

L	Distribution	Parameters (95% CI)	
2	Gamma	$\alpha=1.9156$	$\beta=0.6797$
4	Gamma	$\alpha=3.6046$	$\beta=0.44444$
20	Log-Normal	$\mu=0.60384$	$\sigma=0.26877$
50	Log-Normal	$\mu=0.6572$	$\sigma=0.17372$

Numerical computations of the expected value of equation (1) over the distributions Table 1 scaled by E_b/N_o yield the analytical P_b predictions for spectrally encoded signals. Figure 8 plots the analytical results of the spectrally encoded RAKE receiver P_b .

Figure 8. Analytical Results: Encoded

Analytical Results Summary

When compared graphically, the analytical results demonstrate the gains shown in Table 2 [12]. Gain, G , is defined as the difference in the transmitted E_b/N_o required to achieve the same P_b between the encoded and unencoded signals as shown in (44).

$$G(\text{dB}) = \frac{E_{b,UnEnc}}{N_o}(\text{dB}) - \frac{E_{b,Enc}}{N_o}(\text{dB}) \quad (44)$$

Table 2. Analytically Predicted Gain for Spectrally Encoded Signals [12]

Diversity $-L$	Predicted Gain (dB)
2	~ 1
4	~ 1.75
20	~ 2.5
50	~ 2.75

Simulation

Methodology

Figure 9 displays the system modeled and simulated. The transmitters are as described in Figure 1, and the RAKE receivers are described in Figure 6. The communications channel is modeled as the tapped delay line shown in Figure 3. Since the simulations are at baseband, the AWGN source has a one-sided PSD of N_o .

Figure 9. System Under Test

The system workload is the SNR, E_b/N_o , which is varied to cover analytically predicted P_b of 0.1 to 10^{-5} .

The system parameters, which do not change over the course of the simulations, are chosen based on either previously stated assumptions or to model cell phone channel characteristics in the 900MHz band. As stated earlier, the system is simulating BPSK modulation. The data transmitted is uniformly random. The bit rate for the system is 10kbps to mirror IS-95 cell phone data rates [14]. The fundamental frequency of the system, f_{sb} , is equal to the bit rate at 10kHz. The number of spectral components in the FSWs is selected such that the baseband bandwidth, W_{BB} is wide enough for the channel to be considered frequency-selective. In these simulations $P=1024$. The phase coding of the FSWs, ϕ_p , is pseudo-randomized by a Gold Sequence in order to minimize the autocorrelation of the FSWs. For repeatability, the same Gold Sequence is used in every experiment. The channel is simulated as a Rayleigh faded channel. The channel impulse response coefficients have magnitudes that are Rayleigh distributed with parameter σ . This research assumes that on average, the channel model returns 100% of the transmitted energy. Based on this assumption, the

value of the Rayleigh distribution parameter σ is derived below.

$$1 = \mathbf{E} \left[\int_0^{T_{sb}} |h_l(t)|^2 dt \right] \quad (45)$$

$$1 = \mathbf{E} \left[\int_0^{T_{sb}} \left| \sum_{n=1}^L \alpha_n e^{j\theta_n} \delta(t - nT_{samp}) \right|^2 dt \right]_{\alpha_n} \quad (46)$$

$$1 = \mathbf{E} \left[\sum_{n=1}^L \alpha_n^2 \right]_{\alpha_n} = \mathbf{E} [L \alpha_n^2]_{\alpha_n} = L 2 \sigma^2, \text{ therefore:} \quad (47)$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2L}} \quad (48)$$

Given the system parameters above, the experiments vary factors to match the analysis and compare the performance of spectrally encoded and unencoded signals.

The levels of diversity, L , vary to cover the range of typical and worst-case delay spread suburban cell phone channel environments given in [15]. Using the sampling interval ($T_{samp}=1/[2P f_{sb}]$) and the relationship in (49), Table 3 lists the delay spread, T_{delay} , modeled and corresponding number of delay taps.

$$L = \lfloor T_{delay} / T_{samp} \rfloor + 1 \quad (49)$$

Table 3. Delay Spread vs. Number of Taps

Delay Spread, T_{delay} (μ s)	Delay Taps, L
0.1	2
0.2	4
1	20
2.5	50

Simulation Results

This section presents analytical and simulated P_b curves for each level of L . Each figure plots P_b vs. *transmitted* E_b/N_o . Each plot contains two reference lines, two analytical predictions and two sets of simulation results. The first reference line represents BPSK matched filter performance through a FSSF multipath channel with no diversity (i.e., worst-case). The second reference is a BPSK matched filter in AWGN without multipath fading, representing the theoretical best-case.

L=2 Results

By visual inspection of Figure 10, it is clear that the analytical P_b predictions are consistent with the simulated results. Qualitatively, the simulated spectrally encoded signal has a better P_b than the unencoded signal at each E_b/N_o as predicted. By graphically estimating gain G , the spectrally encoded signals provide approximately 1dB gain over the unencoded signals as seen in the analytical results.

Figure 10. $L=2$: P_b vs. Transmitted E_b/N_o

L=4 Results

The P_b curve for $L=4$ in Figure 11 reveals several qualitative results. Some general comments are in order. The most likely cause for the divergence in the encoded signal results at $E_b/N_o > 12.0$ dB in Figure 11 is an inaccuracy in the analysis. For high E_b/N_o , and low P_b , some assumptions or approximations are invalid. Inaccuracies in the SNR pdf estimation could cause errors in the analytical P_b prediction. Overall, the spectrally encoded signals perform at a lower P_b than the unencoded signals as predicted. For the $L=4$ simulation results, the graphically estimated gain for spectrally encoded vs. unencoded signals is approximately 2dB across the range of P_b plotted. The simulated gain is slightly greater than the analytical gain.

Figure 11. $L=4$: P_b vs. Transmitted E_b/N_o

L=20 Results

The simulation results For $L=20$ in Figure 12 are qualitatively consistent with the analytical results for both the spectrally encoded and unencoded signals. The spectrally encoded signals also perform at a lower P_b than the unencoded signals as predicted. The graphical gain estimation for the simulation results is approximately 2.5dB, the same as estimated for the analytical results. The unencoded P_b curve appears to be converging to the BPSK in AWGN reference line as L increases. Since the research assumptions and simulation design ensure that on average, 100% of the energy transmitted into the channel is passed, then as the diversity increases, it is postulated that the unencoded signals will approach the BPSK in AWGN P_b reference until intersymbol and self-interference terms increase and overcome the benefit of the diversity.

Figure 12. $L=20$: P_b vs. Transmitted E_b/N_o

There is one other trend worth noting in these results. Notice that the spectrally encoded, shaped spectrum signal P_b is better (less) than the reference line for the BPSK matched filter in AWGN only. This effect is caused by the spectral encoding algorithm. The algorithm emphasizes the “amplification” and deemphasizes the “filtering” across the different frequency bands in the channel transfer function spectrum. Therefore the received SNR in the demodulator γ_b is greater than the transmitted SNR E_b/N_o . This phenomenon combined with the diversity from the RAKE receiver is what enables the spectrally encoded, shaped spectrum signal to have a better P_b than the “best-case” reference line.

L=50 Results

Figure 13 contains the analysis and simulation results for $L=50$. As in the previous comparisons of the spectrally encoded and unencoded signals, the analytical results are consistent with the simulation results. The unencoded P_b curves continue to converge toward the BPSK in AWGN reference and the spectrally encoded P_b curves continue to improve beyond the BPSK in AWGN reference. In the $L=50$ simulations, the graphically estimated gain for spectrally encoded versus unencoded signals is slightly above 2.75dB across the range of P_b plotted.

Figure 13. $L=50$: P_b vs. Transmitted E_b/N_o

Conclusions

The goal of the research was achieved. Analysis and simulations compared spectrally encoded and unencoded signal P_b through a FSSF multipath channel using an L -diversity RAKE receiver. The results of both the analysis and simulations are presented with the overall result that spectrally encoded signals have a better (lower) P_b than unencoded signals at the same transmitted E_b/N_o . A range of 1.0dB to 2.75dB gain in transmitted E_b/N_o , depending on the amount of diversity L in the channel and RAKE receiver, is realized in both the analyses and simulations simply by applying spectral encoding to the signals to match the transfer function of the FSSF multipath channel. Additionally, the simulation results verify the analytically predicted P_b for both spectrally encoded and unencoded signals using an L -diversity RAKE receiver.

References

- [1] Gevorgiz, John, et al., April 1994, “Adaptive narrow-band interference rejection in a DS spread-spectrum intercept receiver using transform domain signal processing techniques,” *IEEE Trans. Comm.*, Vol. 37, No. 12, pp. 1359-1366.
- [2] Milstein, Laurence, Panjak Das, January 1983, “An analysis of a real-time transform domain filtering digital communication system--part II: wide-band interference rejection,” *IEEE Trans. On Comm.*, Vol. 31, No. 1, pp. 21–27.

- [3] Nelson, Russell S., Takis Kasparis, 10-13 April 1994, "Digital processing for non-stationary narrow-band interference suppression in fading channels," *Southeastcon '94. 'Creative Technology Transfer - A Global Affair', Proceedings of the 1994 IEEE*. pp. 408-412.
- [4] Falconer, David, et al., April 2002, "Frequency domain equalization for single-carrier broadband wireless systems," *IEEE Comm. Mag.*, Vol. 40, No. 4, pp. 58-66.
- [5] da Silva, Claudio R.C.M., Laurence B. Milstein, 16-19 November 2003, "Spectral-encoded UWB communication systems," *Ultra Wideband Systems and Technologies, 2003 IEEE Conference on*. pp. 96-100.
- [6] Hara Shinsuke, Ramjee Prasad, December 1997, "Overview of multicarrier CDMA," *IEEE Comm. Magazine*, Vol. 35, No. 12, pp 126-133.
- [7] Shayesteh, Mahrokh G., May 2003, "Spread-time CDMA resistance in fading channels," *IEEE Trans. On Comm.*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 446-458.
- [8] Strohmer Thomas, et al., 29 Nov – 3 Dec 2004, "Application of time-reversal with MMSE equalizer to UWB communications," *Global Telecomm. Conference, 2004, GLOBECOM '04, IEEE*, Vol. 5, pp. 3123-3127.
- [9] Øien, Geir E., et al., May 2004, "Impact of channel prediction on adaptive coded modulation performance in Rayleigh fading," *IEEE Trans. On Vehicular Tech.*, Vol. 53, No. 3, pp. 758-769.
- [10] Nunez, Abel, March 2004, Interference Suppression in Multiple Access Communications Using M-ary Phase Shift Keying Generated Using Spectral Encoding. Master's Thesis, Graduate School of Engineering, Air Force Institute of Technology, Wright-Patterson AFB OH, AFIT/GE/ENG/04-20,. Chapters 3-4.
- [11] Proakis, John G., 2001, Digital Communications, Fourth Edition. New York, New York, McGraw Hill, pp. 40, 149, 255, 268, 800-825, 841-847.
- [12] Gaona, Charles M., March 2005, Performance of a Spectrally Encoded Multi-Carrier Phase Shift Keying Communication System in a Frequency-Selective, Slowly-Fading Multipath Channel, Master's Thesis, Graduate School of Engineering, Air Force Institute of Technology, Wright-Patterson AFB OH, AFIT/GE/ENG/05-03, Chapters 3-5.
- [13] Papoulis, Athanasios, S. Unnikrishna Pillai, 2002, Probability, Random Variables, and Stochastic Processes, Fourth Edition, New York, New York, McGraw Hill, pp. 89,131-132, 148, 184, 202-205.
- [14] McKinstry, David R., R. Michael Buehrer, 4-7 August 2002, "Issues in the performance and covertness of UWB communications systems". *The 2002 45th Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems, 2002. MWSCAS-2002.*, Vol. 3, pp. 601-4.
- [15] Rappaport, Theodore S., 1996, Wireless Communications, Principles and Practice, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, Prentice Hall PTR, pp. 139-140, 162-174.

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